

Impact of biofilm in human health

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Biofilms are intricate colonies of microbes adhered to surfaces that are kept together by self-produced polymer matrix mostly made of extracellular DNA, secreted proteins, and polysaccharides. Single-celled microorganisms or a mixture of bacteria, protozoa, archaea, algae, filamentous fungi, and yeast that cling tightly to biotic or abiotic surfaces can form a biofilm. Biofilms have been demonstrated to form in medical environments on the surfaces of medical devices, on dead tissues (such as the sequestra of bones), and inside living tissues (such as the surfaces of teeth and lung tissue). certain biofilms are advantageous to human physiology, eliminating biofilms must be extremely targeted and selective. A higher risk of foodborne infectious diseases may result from the many foodborne germs that can stick to the contact surfaces found in these places. A biofilm can frequently be identified using optical microscopy, but DNA hybridization procedures are the only way to precisely identify every bacterium contained in a biofilm. Biofilms play a critical role in pathogen defence because newly discovered illnesses threaten sustainability, biodiversity, and human health. There is greater debate on the presence of biofilms *sensu stricto* on the walls of the vertebrate digestive tract. *S. aureus* strains isolated from patients and hospital environments, including those with numerous body locations, produced biofilms. This review summarises the mechanism of biofilm and their effects on human health.

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